

Annex II

De Sitter Model

Annex to Kingmakers: life's gateway to the stars

CONTENTS:

When considering transmissions or travels beyond the limits of our galaxy, the expansion of the universe starts to have noticeable effects. Absolute limits of range appear due to the expansion, which settle the accessible universe. The annex *De Sitter Model* develops a constant expansion model allowing to easily estimate elements within reach as a function of the initial speed of the transmission or travel.

In the broader discussion addressed in *Kingmakers: life's gateway to the stars*, this model is used at the stage of evaluation, for the estimation of elements within reach when considering potential impacts beyond our galaxy.

It is also used to evaluate the losses of opportunity due to volume flowing out of reach along the expanding universe.

Table of Contents

Introduction	2
1) Models for cosmology	3
2) de Sitter model	4
3) Resource access	9
a) Volume related: varying as r^3	10
b) Net related: varying as r^6	10
c) (n) Horizons	11
d) Orders of magnitude: varying as $\text{Log}_{10}(x)$	13
4) Loss of opportunity	14
a) Progressive loss due expansion	15
b) Time to a remaining fraction of density within access	15
c) Causal fracturation	18
d) Gravity, locally maintaining causality	20
e) Technological compensation for expansion	20
f) Urging, viewed as a loss of opportunity	22
g) Existential risk and opportunities	22
Bibliography	23

List of tables

<i>Table 1. Distance to horizon as a function of initial speed</i>	5
<i>Table 2. Time to reach a fraction of a distance to horizon</i>	6
<i>Table 3. Distance (ly) above which the expansion has an impact on the travel time, higher than 1%.</i>	8
<i>Table 4. Synthesis on orders of magnitudes</i>	11
<i>Table 5. Elapsed time to remaining fractions of homogeneous distributions</i>	14
<i>Table 6. Percentage of lost accessible universe, as a function of elapsed time</i>	14
<i>Table 7. Time to causal isolation as a function of the considered structure and causation speed.</i>	18
<i>Table 8. Technological progress required to compensate for expansion</i>	20

List of figures

<i>Fig 1. Maximum amount of chained messages (n) as a function of comoving distance from origin, and speed of transmitter, between elements moving with the expansion.</i>	10
<i>Fig 2. Fraction of homogeneous distributions, remaining within reach below horizon, as a function of elapsed time</i>	17
<i>Fig 3. Ratio of amount of solar masses, used to compute the time to isolation.</i>	18
<i>Fig 4. A chronology of causal fracturation</i>	19

Introduction

The purpose of this annex is to focus on the specificities of what lies beyond galactic range. Beyond our Galaxy, the expansion of the universe indeed has effects on transmission and travel time, even for very fast processes, such as signals travelling at lightspeed, or probes travelling at 20% of the speed of light.¹ These effects amplify to reach a point where maximal ranges, called horizons, may not be exceeded, due to the expansion of the universe. As a consequence, while no conclusion shall be proposed regarding the finitude of the universe, the accessible universe is itself limited.

The extragalactic share of this accessible universe, millions of lightyears away, appears extremely distant. Still, it may not be neglected as it embodies the largest domain hosting the potential impacts of the decision we humans may make regarding the spreading of life as we know it on Earth. As we will see below, the volume within the event horizon² is indeed ten thousand billion times larger ($e+14$), than our galactic environment.

In [1\) Models for cosmology](#), we propose an overview of the main perspectives for the future evolution of the universe.

Then, in [2\) De Sitter model](#), we power up our representation with a simple cosmological expansion model, the de Sitter model. This model, coherent with the current paradigm and the Λ CDM model³, allows for the simple calculation of horizons for given processes with an initial

¹ Travel time increased by more than 1%, see 2).

² The event horizon is the horizon calculated at the speed of light. It is the maximal distance reachable by any process limited to this maximum speed.

³ [2] ([Sandberg 2018](#)) [Space races: settling the universe fast](#)

speed, and consequently, permits to estimate the limits of the accessible universe for transmissions and travels.

In section [3\) Resource access](#), we then investigate resource access within these volumes, which allows us to provide estimates for the maximal network size within volume, and for the increase in orders of magnitude, for homogeneous distributions within volume. This provides us with ways to estimate the maximal opportunities for the development of resource limited self-reproducing things, such as life as we know it, and allows us to investigate what it would mean, for life as we know it on Earth, to gain access to the extrasolar environment, beyond galactic range.

In part [4\) Loss of opportunity](#), considering how the expansion of the universe is removing material and energy out of sight and access, we will investigate the question of lost opportunities with elapsed time, and reply to the question of the technological pace required to compensate for this loss, with an increase of speed for the vectors. The issue of the universe progressively turning into a causal patch, following the progressive isolation of gravitationally bound structures will be addressed.

1) Models for cosmology

Current cosmological models propose a variable expansion of the universe. Objects accelerate away from each other. While there is an agreement on the current expansion, depending on the literature, the universe may be expanding with varying levels of acceleration depending on its age, and even be contracting at some point. Here below are the main hypothesis:

- *(H) Big freeze: infinite expansion and cooling*
- *(H) Big rip: accelerated expansion until dislocation of spacetime*
- *(H) Big crunch: after some time, the universe start collapsing on itself*
- *(H) Big bounce: following a big crunch, the universe may bounce*
- *(H) Multiple big crunch: local crunches and bounces may happen*
- *(H) Conformal cyclic cosmology: any of the above starts with a big bang initiated in the later ages of a preceding universe of the same type*

In the future, depending on the behaviour of the model universe, an event horizon may exist, beyond which no causation can occur, due to the universe expanding at a speed faster than the maximal speed for the considered process, at a large scale. When an absolute speed limit is set

for all causal processes, this sheds an absolute boundary for causality. This horizon, beyond which causality is broken, is classically defined with transmitters being non-massive, hence with information travelling at the speed of light. At some distance, the universe is expanding faster than this ultimate speed. While counterintuitive, this is possible because the maximum achievable speed as proposed by Einstein equations is only a limit in local coordinates. In the standard model of cosmology, which is of the big freeze type, dominated by dark-matter and dark-energy, and referred to as the Λ CDM model, we have:

$$H_{\lambda\text{CDM}, t=0}^{\Rightarrow} / \text{Any causality} = 4\,823.66 \text{ Mpc} = 15.7 \text{ Gly}^4$$

In this model, the horizon is reached by any non massive vector, in about $1e11$ years or so⁵. When this happens an absolute causal separation occurs between gravitationally bound clusters, and the causal structure of the universe ends up fractured, as a causal patch.

In the big crunch, bounce and multiple crunch hypothesis, horizons may do fancy things that might be worth investigating.

The simple de Sitter model proposed further below gives us $9e10$ years to this separation, which is coherent with the Λ CDM proposition.

2) de Sitter model

For our purpose of building a synthetic representation, the de Sitter model is particularly interesting, because while being an acceptable approximation to the later cosmological areas, coherent with the Λ CDM Model and the current paradigm⁶, it is easy to manipulate formally, being extremely simple and depicting mainly the expansion itself. As such, it allows us to approximate the causal consequences of the expansion in future time.

Majors hypothesis for the de Sitter model are:

- Isotropic, homogeneous universe
- Expansion rate is constant across time
- No gravitation, no mass content, hence no celestial mechanics, no stars nor stellar evolution.

⁴ [1] (Margalef-Bentabol et al. 2012) [Evolution of the cosmological horizons in a concordance universe](#)

⁵ [2] (Sandberg 2018) [Space races: settling the universe fast](#)

⁶ See Main document, Glossary, Paradigm, and [2] (Sandberg 2018) [Space races: settling the universe fast](#)

This allows for an easy calculation for causality governed by processes with an initial speed v_0 , as a function of H , which is the Hubble constant, approximated in 2019 to be $H = 74,03 \pm 1,42$ km/s/Mpc.

Here below are detailed multiple formulas and applications, useful to our considerations:

Distance traversed:

In this model the comoving distance traversed s , by a vector with an initial speed v_0 , behaves as $s(t) = (v_0/H)(1 - \exp(-Ht))$.

Arrival Time:

The arrival time t at distance L is $t(L) = -(1/H) * \ln(1 - HL/v_0)$.

Horizon:

The horizon at any given initial speed v_0 , as the limit of $s(t)$ when t tends towards infinity, is consequently calculated as follow:

$$H_{de\ Sitter, t=0}^{\Rightarrow} / (v_0) = v_0/H$$

Some interesting horizons calculated as such, are:

Table 1. Distance to horizon as a function of initial speed		
	Vo (km/s)	Distances (ly)
Event horizon	300000	13E+9 ly
Starshot horizon (20%c)	60000	2,6E+9 ly
Milky Way escape speed horizon	550	24E+6 ly
Horizon Voyager 1 (> Voyager 2)	17	7,6E+5 ly
<i>To compare with:</i>		
Solar System escape speed	16,6 km/s	
Milky Way radius	5,3E+4 ly	
Closest Galaxy (Andromeda)	2.5E+6 ly	

If the horizons for Voyager 1&2 do not really make sense because these probes are gravitationally bound to the Milky way, which is likely to hold together despite of expansion, we can note here that the speed envisioned for Starshot project (20%c) is higher than the Galaxy escape speed. At such a speed, intergalactic causality may happen up to an horizon a thousand times larger than the distance to the next galaxy.

Time to horizon: infinite

It takes an infinite time for a process to reach its horizon.

Elapsed time as a function of the reached fraction of horizon:

The time required to get to a fraction of the horizon can be calculated in the below way:

$$\begin{aligned}
 t(X\% * H \xrightarrow{\text{de Sitter, } t=0} / (v_0)) &= t(X\% * v_0/H) \\
 &= -(1/H) * \ln(1 - X\% * v_0/H * H/v_0) \\
 &= -(1/H) * \ln(1 - X\%)
 \end{aligned}$$

It is interesting to note that with this model, the minimum time for causality to reach a given percentage of the distance to the causal horizon is not dependent on the initial speed of the transmitter. Also, as plotted on Fig.1, the time to reach a given fraction of the distance to horizon is quasi linear up to distances of about 75% of the horizon, increasing rapidly when considering further distances.

Fig.1 Time to reach a fraction of the distance to horizon

Interesting numbers are proposed in table 2:

Distance reached/horizon	Time to reach (y)	
	99%	60 billion yr
	50%	9 billion yr
	10%	1.3billion yr
	1%	132 million yr
One thousands of the distance to horizon:E-06		13 million yr
One millionth of the distance to horizon:E-06		13.300 yr
One billionth of the distance to horizon: E-09		13 yr

The duration of the journeys are only significantly impacted by expansion, when compared with a static universe where $t(L) = L/v_0$, after a certain distance, which is a function of the initial speed. The useful distances, numerically solved, are proposed:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Distance to a 0.1\% difference} &= v_0/(490 * H) \approx 0.2\% * \text{Horizon}(v_0) & \text{Elapsed time} &= 30E + 6yr \\
 \text{Distance to a 1\% difference} &= v_0/(50.9 * H) \approx 2\% * \text{Horizon}(v_0) & \text{Elapsed time} &= 0.3E + 9yr \\
 \text{Distance to a 10\% difference} &= v_0/(5.67 * H) \approx 17\% * \text{Horizon}(v_0) & \text{Elapsed time} &= 3E + 9yr
 \end{aligned}$$

Travelling at lightspeed to Andromeda, our closest galactic neighbor, the difference in journey time due to expansion is about 1/1000 at light speed, 1% at 20%c, and 6% at the Milky way gravity well escape speed.

For our purpose, we propose that a 1% difference is a reasonable threshold below which a static universe may be used. The below distances are calculated, beyond which expansion start to have noticeable effects:

Table 3. Distance (ly) above which the expansion has an impact on the travel time, higher than 1%. (reached after 0.3e+9yr)

	Distance (ly)
At the speed of light	26e+7 ly
At 20% of the speed of light (20%c)	5e+7 ly
At Milky Way escape speed	48e+4 ly
<i>To compare with</i>	
Milky Way radius	5e+4 ly
Closest galaxy (Andromeda)	2.5e+6 ly

>> From these results, it appears that the effect of the expansion of the universe may not be neglected when considering distances beyond our Galaxy.

3) Resource access

In this section, we will question how volume related distribution may be accessed as a function of r^3 then how dual interactions approximate in r^6 and how the overall quantity of those dual interactions are limited by distances, with the concept of a (n)horizon, defining the distance above which a maximum of n interactions is possible. Questioning the increase from the point of view of orders of magnitude, we will outline how volume related properties, and interaction related properties, respectively increase three times and six times faster than the increase of the order of magnitude for range.

Having developed these elements, I will address the question of resource access for exponentially relevant inferences as developed in XXX, and put in perspective what it would mean, for life as we know it, understood as a self replicating inference, to be released to the extrasolar environment.

a) Volume related: varying as r^3

Following the assumption that the universe is isotropic at large scales, the approximation can be made that at any large scale regarding a given distribution, its repartition is homogenous and can be simply described by a density parameter ρ . Should the access be possible for life until a given distance, the quantity impacted is then simply $\rho \cdot (4/3)r^3$. As such, the ultimate mass of matter possibly reassembled by life, the amount of possible stellar systems impacted by life, or the potentially available stellar energy for its astronomical flourishing, are increasing in a cubic way with the radius of the considered space within reach. As an example, we could use this to estimate the quantity of solar masses relevant to the analysis, by using the critical density of ordinary matter from the Λ CDM model: 4.08×10^{-28} kg/m³, and the volume contained within the event horizon, which would lead to a potential of approximately 10^{21} stellar systems possibly impacted by whatever might eventually be outbound from the Solar System.

b) Net related: varying as r^6

When you're alone, you've no interaction. When you are two at the table. You get 1 possible link. When you are three, you get 4 possibilities. 4 of you get 16 possibilities. Let's define a link as a minimum of one returned message. Considering a sphere with a diameter permitting one exchange with a response, between the most extreme part of this sphere, then the sphere containing N inferences allows for C_n^k possible links. As such, the amount of possible interactions is exploding with the size of the assessed sphere.

C_n^k can be bounded with the following expressions: $\frac{n^k}{k^k} \leq C_n^k \leq \frac{n^k}{k!}$

Which implies, with $k=2$, and $n = \rho \cdot \frac{4}{3}\pi r^3$, that the amount of links within a sphere containing an homogeneous distribution described by a density parameter ρ is bounded by:

$$\left(\frac{1}{3}\rho\pi\right)^2 r^6 \leq C_{\left(\frac{4}{3}\rho\pi r^3\right)}^2 \leq \left(\frac{2}{3}\rho\pi\right)^2 r^6$$

c) (n) Horizons

The thing is: a horizon may exist for the possibility of feedback on causation. Downstream, objects might be accessible to transmissions or spaceships without any possibility to ever know the outcome. Upstream, this means one might observe something, receive a message or experience a consequence and never be able to respond. Let's define this as the (n)Horizon. With n being the number of messages in the exchange: n=1 means the horizon for a causation with no feedback, a message with no reply, or an outbound cause for the originator, with no consequence apart from the one of having no possible causal return from the destination. n=2 means the horizon for having one feedback in return

n is odd for all horizon with the last message sent having no possible feedback

n is even, for any horizon with an ultimate feedback

For any given target, the (1) Horizon is the conventional horizon. With n being the number of messages in the exchange, we get :

$${}^{(n)}H_{de\ Sitter, t=0}^{\Rightarrow} / (v_0) = v_0 / (nH)$$

Which allows us to compute simply, the maximum quantity of chained messages(n) as a function of comoving distance from origin, and speed of transmitter. This is plotted on Fig 1. When a feedback horizon exists, at distances shorter than the feedback horizon, exchange may happen, and the maximal amount of exchanges increases with diminishing distances.

Figure 1 below is proposed to allow for the handy evaluation of the maximal amount of chained messages exchanged with a distant location, when this location is moving away with the expanding universe. The duration of the first travel or transmission may easily be extracted from the column *time to reach (yr)*, as well as the fraction reached, of the distance to the horizon.

Example of use (dashed line): A maximum of 1000 chained signals travelling at the speed of light will ever be exchanged with the gravitationally bound part of the closest cluster (Central part of Virgo Supercluster, 10-20 Mly away), the first of these taking about 13 Myr (scale: Time to reach) to reach its destination, at a fraction of about 1/1000 (e-3) of the distance to the horizon at this speed. A little more than 100 exchanges may happen at 20%c at such distance (amber line), and a single feedback at the Milky Way escape speed (red line).

Fig 1. Maximum amount of chained messages (n) as a function of comoving distance from origin, and speed of transmitter, between elements moving with the expansion.

Notes:

- Shaded area corresponds to gravitationally bound elements
- Dashed line corresponds to example of use
- **Caution 1:** this calculus is only valid for structures moving out with the flow of expansion, and consequently, from the Solar System perspective, for elements unbound to us gravitationally. The grey shaded area corresponds to the local group, we are considered bound to.
- **Caution 2:** due to the solar system escape speed being lower than the MilkyWay escape Speed, no causation may escape the Milky Way at that speed.

d) Orders of magnitude: varying as $\text{Log}_{10}(x)$

It is interesting to evaluate how orders of magnitude are multiplied, when the range of access is increased. When magnitude is defined as $Magnitude(X) = \text{Log}_{10}(X)$, let's call ΔMag the change of orders or magnitude:

$$\Delta Mag = \text{Log}_{10}(f(r)) - \text{Log}_{10}(f(r_1)) = \text{Log}_{10}\left(\frac{f(r)}{f(r_1)}\right)$$

Then if $f(r)$ is a function of the type $f(r) : r \rightarrow Ar^K$

$$\Delta Mag(f(r), (r_1, r_0)) = K \text{Log}_{10}(r_1/r_0)$$

And for $f(r) : r \rightarrow Ar^{K_f}$ and $g(r) : r \rightarrow Br^{K_g}$,

$$\frac{\Delta Mag(f(r), (r_1, r_0))}{\Delta Mag(g(r), (r_1, r_0))} = K_f/K_g$$

As a synthesis, the table 4 is proposed:

Table 4. Synthesis on orders of magnitudes
<i>Whenever the range is changed from R_0 to R_1,</i>
Any quantity proportional to distance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • get r_1/r_0 bigger • is increased by $\text{Log}_{10}(r_1/r_0)$ orders of magnitude
Any quantity proportional to volume <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increases proportionally to $(r_1/r_0)^3$ • Has an order of magnitude increasing three times faster than the one of distances: $\Delta Magnitude(Volumes) \propto 3 \times \Delta Magnitude(Distances)$
Any quantity proportional to the quantity of interaction within a distribution of inferences whose quantity is proportional to volume <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increases proportionally to $(r_1/r_0)^6$ • Has an order of magnitude increasing six times faster than the one of distances $Max \Delta Magnitude(Réseaux) \propto 6 \times \Delta Magnitude(Distances)$

4) Loss of opportunity

In some of the media, amongst which Forbes, the urgency for reaching to the outer space is motivated by the rate of loss of opportunity, which is presented as being high:

- “97%⁷ or 98%⁸ of the galaxies in our observable Universe are already out of humanity's reach. This result is exactly the same as mine with the de Sitter model, with causality travelling at c : (My results: at C : 97,77%)
- “with every year that goes by, approximately five entire galaxies cross over that threshold from being reachable to no longer being reachable”⁹. My results: about one Milky way size galaxy.
- Ultimately, in about $1e+11$ years, access will be restricted to the Milky way, or to its merger with colliding galaxies.

In this section, we investigate this question of lost opportunities, due to things expanding over the causal horizon. First I calculate the relative loss per year [\(a\)](#) and see how it is independent of the causation speed and the considered horizon. From there we relate the elapsed time [\(b\)](#), with the remaining fraction of things inside the event horizon. The eventual situation of a causal patch is investigated [\(c\)](#). Gravity, by binding together some of the lower scales structures, is envisioned as a prolongator for causality, and a chronology is proposed for the causal fracturation [\(d\)](#). The possibility of technological safeguarding of opportunities for causation at speed lower than C is investigated [\(e\)](#), and waiting is envisioned in a resource-constrained world, as a valuable way of safeguarding opportunities. [\(f\)](#) Eventually, the discussion regarding opportunities is put in perspective with the question of existential risk. [\(g\)](#)

⁷ [4] [\(Siegel 2018\) The Universe Is Disappearing. And There's Nothing We Can Do To Stop It](#)

⁸ [5] [\(Siegel 2018\) Ask Ethan: How Many Galaxies Have Already Disappeared From Our Perspective?](#)

⁹ [5] [\(Siegel 2018\) Ask Ethan: How Many Galaxies Have Already Disappeared From Our Perspective?](#)

a) Progressive loss due expansion

Using the de Sitter model, whose results are coherent with the numbers above, we get that the fraction of space (hence stars, galaxies, dark matter...) going out of reach each year, beyond any horizon R , is given by:

$$\text{Relative Loss/Year} = Q_{\text{loss}}/A$$

$$\text{With } A = \rho * 4/3 \pi R^3 \text{ and } Q_{\text{loss}} = \rho * H_0 R * 4\pi R^2$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{Relative Loss/Year} = \rho * H_0 * 4\pi R^3 / (\rho * 4/3 \pi R^3)$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{Relative Loss/Year} = 3H_0$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{Relative Loss/Year} = 5e-10 \text{ yr}^{-1}$$

About a billionth of the possible causal access, is lost every 5 months. This loss of opportunity due expansion is quite slow, when thinking with the global picture in mind. It is interesting to note that this loss is independent of the considered horizon R , and hence, that this pace of relative loss is independent of the considered causation type.

b) Time to a remaining fraction of density within access

When as proposed above, $\text{Relative Loss} = 3H_0$ the elapsed time $Et(F)$ to the moment where only a given F fraction of density is remaining within the horizon, is given by the equation:

$$F = (1 - 3H_0)^{Et(F)}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow Et(F) * \ln((1 - 3H_0)) = \ln(F)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow Et(F) = \frac{\ln(F)}{\ln(1-3H_0)} \quad (1)$$

When the considered fraction is related to homogeneous densities at all scales, if H is the horizon for the considered process, and S is the radius of a considered structure, the time to the isolation of this structure is given as a function of S/H :

$$\Rightarrow Et(F) = \frac{3\ln(S/H)}{\ln(1-3H_0)} \quad (2)$$

It is in my opinion very interesting to note that the relative loss per year, expressed in the above paragraph, and the the elapsed time to a remaining fraction (1), are not dependent on the considered horizon: it being the causal access at C or at reduced speed, the relative loss is always the same, and directly a function of H_0 .

After $Et(F)$, only a fraction F of all volume related properties remain within access, and this, independently of the transmitter speed.

Table 5. Elapsed time to remaining fractions of homogeneous distributions

Fraction of homogeneous distributions, remaining within reach below horizon	Elapsed time (years)
99%	40 Myr
50%	3 Gyr
1%	20 Gyr

Note: this is independent of the causation speed

This equation can be interestingly used, to compute the percentage of lost volumetric opportunities due expansion, for any given duration. In table 6, is presented the percentage of lost accessible volume, as a function of interesting durations from an evolutionary standpoint.

Table 6. Percentage of lost accessible universe, as a function of elapsed time

	Time to extrasolar capability (in years)	Percentage of lost accessible volume, during that time frame
From the earliest hominids	7,200,000	0.2%
From multicellular animals	6.50E+08	14%
From cyanobacteria	3.50E+09	55%
From Earth formation	4.50E+09	64%

Elements may be outlined from these results when looking back to history: during the time taken from the possibility of life on Earth, to spacefaring life, 64% of the opportunities have been lost. But the most interesting insight is given ahead, should one retain the hypothesis that when starting anew, evolution takes a comparable duration, to achieve comparable progresses (a range of hypothesis referred to as the copernican astrobiological principle¹⁰, and used extensively in the Drake equation literature). Indeed, this table provides us with a direct insight into the magnitude of the opportunity loss, should a cataclysmic setback occur. A cataclysm eradicating mankind and setting life back to the developmental stage of apes, who would then take a similar time to the one we took to achieve extrasolar capability, would generate less than a percent of lost opportunities due to expansion. From the point of view of life, a “*Planet of the Apes*” scenario wouldn’t be a terrific harm, while any setback beyond the stage of multicellular animals would be dramatical: not only the lost accessible volume start to be noticeable, but also, the time required to reevolve to interstellar capability is longer than the survivability on Earth, limited to about a billion years ahead due to the natural increase in solar luminosity, eventually inducing a thermal runaway and leading to the complete evaporation of oceans¹¹.

c) Causal fracturation

According to this analysis, in three billions years from now, any place in the universe will be isolated from 50% of what it can access now, and in 20 billion years, it will be isolated from 99% of it. Worse, **in about e+11 years, the universe ends up entirely fractured, and everything is isolated from everything**, in what the literature refers to as a causal patch. The results presented here are consistent with the results from the LCDM model, which give a time limit of e+11 years, and are presented in Figure 2, presenting the remaining fraction of homogeneous distributions, within reach below horizon, as a function of elapsed time.

¹⁰ [6] (Westby and Conselice 2020) [The Astrobiological Copernican Weak and Strong Limits...](#)

¹¹ [7] (Leconte et al. 2013) [Increased insolation threshold for runaway greenhouse processes...](#)

Fig 2. Fraction of homogeneous distributions, remaining within reach below horizon, as a function of elapsed time

This looks very theoretical, and to me, consequences are difficult to grasp. To get a clearer view, I propose to focus on scales of known structures in the universe, such as stellar systems, galaxies, and clusters. To compute this in a simple way, as presented in figure 3 below, the formulae above were used with the ratio of solar masses within the event horizon, between the present time, and the moment at which only the considered structure is remaining within the horizon.

Fig 3. Ratio of amount of solar masses, used to compute the time to isolation

The time to causal isolation is dependent on the transmitter speed, due to the associated event horizon changing with the corresponding speed:

Table 7. Time to causal isolation as a function of the considered structure and causation speed.

<i>Considered structure</i>	<i>Mass (Solar masses)</i>	<i>Time to causal isolation</i>			
		<i>At C (yr)</i>	<i>At 20%c (yr)</i>	<i>At Milky Way escape speed</i>	<i>At Solar System escape speed</i>
Stellar System (Solar System size)	1E+00	2E+11	2E+11	1E+11	8E+10
Galaxy (Milky Way size)	1E+12	9E+10	7E+10	1E+10	Already isolated
Super cluster (Virgo supercluster size)	1E+15	6E+10	4E+10	Already isolated	Already isolated
Laniakea supercluster size)	1E+17	4E+10	2E+10	Already isolated	Already isolated

d) Gravity, locally maintaining causality

The causal fracturation discussed above is calculated within a de Sitter model, and as such, is bound to happen between elements moving with the cosmic flow of the expansion. The speed of structures within the universe, is likely to modify those conclusions. Also, some structures are gravitationally bound. For example, our Solar System, and our Galaxy, will presumably hold together thanks to gravity. The causal structure is consequently likely to be maintained, thanks to gravity, within those structures, and similar ones.

With this in mind, Figure 4 is proposed as a chronology of causal fracturation:

Fig 4. A chronology of causal fracturation

>> 10 billions years ahead, the minimal speed for intergalactic travel gets higher than the galactic escape speeds. 70 billions years ahead, spaceships at 20%*c* are restricted to galaxy size movement. In about 100 billions years, galaxies will be isolated, even for communications. Later than this, only gravitationally bound structures may stay relevant to each other.

>> it is interesting to note that gravity, from this perspective, acts as a prolongator for causality.

e) Technological compensation for expansion

While the loss is unavoidable for signals travelling at *C*, due to the impossibility to accelerate further, the question is raised whether a technological increase in spaceship speed could compensate for the expansion of the universe and maintain opportunities, for some time. Lets calculate the evolution *dv* of the speed *V₀* so that the horizon for *V₀* is increased in such a way that it compensates for the expansion of the universe during *dt*, which is happening at *V* at the position of the horizon. This give the below equation:

To reach the same place with a time shift dt, departing dt later, and arriving dt later, the speed modification dv within dt must satisfy:

$$R_{Sitter}^{t_0+dt \Rightarrow t_1+dt} (v_0 + dv) = R_{Sitter}^{t_0 \Rightarrow t_1} (v_0) + V dt ,$$

$$\text{with : } V = H_0 R \text{ at } R = R_{Sitter}^{t_0 \Rightarrow t_1}(v_0)$$

$$\Rightarrow R_{Sitter}^{t_0+dt \Rightarrow t_1+dt}(v_0 + dv) = R_{Sitter}^{t_0 \Rightarrow t_1} + H_0 R_{Sitter}^{t_0 \Rightarrow t_1}(v_0)dt$$

$$\text{In a de Sitter universe, } R_{Sitter}^{t_0 \Rightarrow t}(v_0) = (v_0/H_0)(1 - e^{-H_0 t})$$

$$\text{And: } R_{Sitter}^{t_0+dt \Rightarrow t_1+dt}(x) = R_{Sitter}^{t_0 \Rightarrow t_1}(x) \text{ in comoving coordinates.}$$

$$\Rightarrow (v_0 + dv)/H_0 * (1 - e^{-H_0(t_1+dt)}) = (1 - e^{-H_0 t_1}) * (v_0/H_0 + H_0 v_0/H_0 dt)$$

$$\Rightarrow dv/dt = H_0 v_0$$

From this equation, for any vector speed, in order to keep the capacity for reaching any given reach or horizon in a de Sitter universe, the technological progress should allow for a ratio of increase of vector speed of : $(dv/dt)/v_0 = H_0$

Table 8. Technological progress required to compensate for expansion

Ratio of requested speed increase per year so as to keep the access to a given region:	7.6e-9% per year
Duration after which a 1% vector speed increased must have happened, so as to keep access to any given region, in years:	1.3e+08 yr
Duration after which a 50% vector speed increased must have happened, so as to keep access to any given region, in years:	7e+09 yr

>> It appears the technological progress pace required to compensate for the loss of opportunity due the expansion of the universe, is ridiculously low. For any given vector slower than C, the required progress in speed only of about 1% every 130 million years !

f) Urging, viewed as a loss of opportunity

As an interesting complementary view, Robert L. Forward proposed that the sole fact that technological speed improvement allows for faster mission, is a sufficient argument for waiting: by waiting for better technology, any target would indeed be reached faster in the end. For him, for this reason, no mission should be undertaken that cannot be completed within 50 years, indeed, such an effort would to his research divest the resources for technological advancement

that would otherwise allow for a faster travel. From this point of view, by defunding future faster travel, mankind would actually lose opportunities by urging for interstellar travel.

g) Existential risk and opportunities

From the above considerations, it appears that for causation at speed slower than C , not only the effect of the expansion is easily overcome by even a very slow technological progress (4-e), but also that urging actually represents a non-intuitive loss of opportunity (4-f).

Still, those considerations rely on the hypothesis of technological progress, and of course, of existence. As such, an informed decision regarding waiting, should bear in consideration the risks of technological stagnation or collapse. In his 2019 Starship briefing, E. Musk clearly states this later element in his rhetoric for the colonisation of Mars: one of the reasons we should do it now, is that there is no way we can guarantee it will still be possible in the future. An interesting insight given by the above development is regarding the cost of opportunity for the disappearance or impairment of life. Should life be eradicated from Earth somehow today, with no possibility ever to restart, the loss of opportunity would equate to the entire accessible universe as of today. But in a more probable situation where life is capable of rebooting, from leftovers, or thanks to the conditions that would be favorable, it is interesting to note that the 3.5 billions of years demonstrated development time, required to get to today's development stage of nearing interstellar capability, is in the same order of magnitude as the time required to lose 50% of potential access to this very same universe (4-b).

>> Should life be set back to early ages today, and should the copernican astrobiological principle apply¹², the loss of opportunity for expansion in space would be somewhere about 50%

¹² [6] [\(Westby and Conselice 2020\) The Astrobiological Copernican Weak and Strong Limits...](#)

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